

INFORMATION POLICIES AND LAWS EMPHASIZING DATA PROTECTION LAWS IN UNITED STATES: A STUDY

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Abstract:

Information privacy is responsible and works for the misuse of information as well as data of a particular person or a kind of organization. Among the international player, Europe is an name for taking necessary steps about information. Most of the countries as well as independent region Europe and many in Latin America and the Caribbean, Asia, and Africa, have adopted data protection laws due to its important and benefits. The United States has a comprehensive information privacy law, but with some limitations. All over the world every organization has information and in different forms and managing this information and its protection is important and valuable. It is worthy that Europe and nearest nations have enacted different kind of data protection laws for the disclosure as well as misuse of information. 80 + countries as well as independent region in different continents now a days having this kind of laws and regulation. Though important is the United States is noted for not having an extensive law but rather having enacted different kind of but limited sectoral laws. The privacy laws of the United States deal with several different legal concepts. This is a conceptual paper and mainly deals with the affairs of Data Protection Laws in United States.

Keywords: Information Polices, Data Protection Act, IT Act, United States, Information Divide, Digitalization, Information Literacy, Information Assurance

Introduction

Information Policy is actually deals with the phases that the information goes by way of beginning with its creation. Information policy became an important study area and domain in the late of 20th century during the transition of industrial to Information Society. The growing and advanced Information Policy system has enhanced this is as a field of studies even in many countries. In Information Policy, the laws and regulations related to the information and data is most valuable. Information Policy is a broader field including the areas drawn from computer security, information privacy, internet etc multitude of components [1], [5]. The Information Policy has importance into different fields and it related with the Information Science in some extend. In Information Law and Policy different subjects are covered which are helpful for the data protection. The main reason for the need of Information Policy deals with the legal issues that can be connecting with the advancement of technology. Among the countries engaged in Information Law and Privacy, United States is important and most valuable [2], [3]. In Data protection and laws role of local government and central government both are important into their respective situation. Data localization, regulation viz. HIPPA, COPPA etc are also important and valuable in most respect.

Objectives

The core and the fundamental goals of this chapter/ paper are includes (but not limited to the following)—

- To know about the Information Privacy and Law in brief and basic sense.
- To learn about the role, need as well as importance of Data protection law and information policy.
- To know about the data localization and its need in relation to the data protection law and practice.
- To learn about the role of local government and central government and their role into the data privacy and protection.
- To learn about the Data Protection Law and Privacy Law in United States and other countries.
- To know about the basics of COPPA, HIPPA, FCRA etc

Fig 1: Information Governance Framework at a glance

Needs of information privacy

Privacy is a kind of secrecy of an individual or group to keep apart themselves, or information nearby themselves. Information privacy system is the concept and procedure for securing the information and content. It is important that something is private to a person or group and it generally sometimes essentially special or sensitive. The information privacy partially deals with the security and a kind of concepts for using appropriate use and protection of information and contents [4], [7]. Privacy may also considered as physical security, the Data Protection Act, Europe itself says about the privacy principles of following types (refer Fig: 2).

Fig 2: The core Data protection principles at a glance (gov.uk)

Data localization:

Data localization is an important and valuable concept which is required for the spreading of data among nations' citizens, importantly data localization law requires data about a nations' citizens and here local privacy data protection is very important and valuable. Data localization needs further steps in claiming of collection, processing and storage of information in occur first within the national boundaries [6], [8].

Role of government in Information Policy:

Every kind of policy basically formulated by the government and here role of Government is most important and valuable, virtually the Information Policy needs to be governed and regulate it. In Information Policy government has huge roles and responsibilities. It is important that providing information with healthy producing and maintaining of information including protecting the privacy and confidentiality of personal and sensitive information are many ways depends on information. Among the important agenda herewith the conceptual framework for the Personal Data Protection Act in Fig. 3.

Fig 3: Main agenda of Personal Data Protection Act

Data Protection with Fundamentals:

The basic principles of data protection laws are different types but the core and fundamentals are include following (but not limited to the)—

- Information collected can't be forwarded to anyone even if authorized by law or after permission of the individual.
- All kind of records should be documented of an individual with all types of accuracy and updating information.
- There should be proper and healthy mechanisms for individuals for the review of data as well as ensuring accuracy.
- All kind of information and data should be deleted/ removed when data and information not required.
- Data protection is done by the manual as well as technological way and tools in different way.

Data laws in different countries with reference to US:

Many countries have already started to implemented information privacy law or data protection law on its region. Among these countries few important are Canada, France, Germany, Switzerland, United Kingdom, and United State to build information privacy law

[9], [11]. These countries make the information privacy or data protection law on the reason on-

- There should be a started reason for all kind of collected data, information and knowledge.
- For arrangement of data and information for sustainable development information culture.
- Protection similar data or contents from another authority or organization.
- For making a suitable information policy and management for the complete information transparencies.
- To determine the data in its own region of an organization and institutions or company
- To avoid the cyber crime and internet offences at large.

Among the important laws for information privacy and data protection enacted in United States few important are include—

- *Health Insurance Portability Act (HIPA).*
- *Fair Credit Reporting Act (FCRA).*
- *Electronic Communication Privacy Act (ECPA).*
- *Computer Security, Privacy and Criminal Law.*
- *Children Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA).*

United States

Data privacy law or concept is not highly legislated or systematic in the U.S. Actually access to private data may be gathered when third-party credit reports may be availed. Most importantly, similar services may be sought on medical care, housing etc. Although partial act exist, there is no all- surround law regulating the act, storage, or use of personal data in the U.S. Please refer Fig: 4 to learn about the Information Governance systems [5], [10]. The Table: 1 whereas specified the common and initiated laws in US.

Table: 1- Privacy related act passed in United States

Act Passed in US related to Information Privacy	Year
U.S. Fair Credit Reporting Act	1970
U.S. Racketeer Influenced and Corrupt Organization (RICO) Act	1970
Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA)	1974
U.S. Privacy Act	1974
Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development	1980

(OECD) Guidelines	
U.S. Medical Computer Crime Act	1984
U.S. Federal Computer Crime Act (strengthened in 1986 and 1994)	1984
U.S. Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (amended in 1986, 1994, 1996 and 2001)	1986
U.S. Electronic Communications Privacy Act (ECPA)	1986
U.S. Computer Security Act (Repealed by the Federal Information Security Management Act of 2002)	1987
U.S. Video Privacy Protection Act	1988
United Kingdom Computer Misuse Act	1990
U.S. Federal Sentencing Guidelines	1991
OECD Guidelines to Serve as a Total Security Framework	1992
Communications Assistance for Law Enforcement Act	1994
Council Directive on Data Protection for the European Union (EU)	1995
U.S. Economic and Protection of Proprietary Information Act	1996
Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) (requirement added in December 2000)	1996
U.S. Digital Millennium Copyright Act (DMCA)	1998
U.S. Uniform Computer Information Transactions Act (UCITA)	1999
U.S. Congress Electronic Signatures in Global National Commerce Act ("ESIGN")	2000
U.S. Provide Appropriate Tools Required to Intercept and Obstruct Terrorism (PATRIOT) Act	2001
Homeland Security Act (HSA)	2002
Federal Information Security Management Act of 2002	2002

FCRA (Fair Credit Reporting Act)

FCRA stands for Fair credit reporting act, it is actually a kind of information privacy act enacted in USA in 1970. Few liabilities of FCRA regulation are include but not limited to the following—

- *Consumer reporting act.*
- *User of consumer report.*
- *Furnisher of consumer information.*

Some of the violence of Fair credit reporting act regulation may include (but not limited to the)

- (1) *Damage of product of services.*
- (2) *Alternative cost.*
- (3) *Court cost.*

Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA)

The Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA) has been enacted in the year 2000 to protect the privacy of children under 13. The U.S. Congress initiated the act in the year 1998 but effected in April 2000. More deeply the COPPA has been managed by the Federal Trade Commission (FTC).

The Act specifies:

- Parental consent for the collection or use of any personal information of young are must in COPPA.
- When and how to seek verifiable consent from a parent or guardian.
- What responsibilities the operator of a Web site legally holds with regards to children's privacy and safety online, including restrictions on the types and methods of marketing targeting those under 13.

Conclusion

Cyber and Information Privacy is an important concern for better and healthy information management and today each and every type of organizations and institutes are facing challenges on information security and thus related awareness program has been initiated. The security concept has broaden enough in last decade and many areas has been developed viz. mobile security, mobile security and risk management is the major concern of current age. In the Information age several products are associated with the digital tools and technologies and thus Digital Age are also improving with side by side with laws and act enacted by the government of different countries.

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